

A PROJECT REPORT ON
**AN ASSESSMENT OF WORK –RELATED STRESS AND ITS IMPACT
ON MESCOM WORKERS IN UDUPI –MANIPAL**

BY

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The project Report has been prepared under the supervision and guidance of Prof. Venkatesh Shetty, Assistant Professor, Poornaprajna Institute of Management, Udupi.

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During this period her conduct and character were found to be commendable. We wish her all the success in her academic career

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ABSTRACT

Work-related stress has become a growing concern in organizations, particularly in essential service sectors like electricity supply, where uninterrupted service delivery is crucial. This study examines the determinants and impact of stress among MESCOM employees in Udupi–Manipal, focusing on how working conditions, organizational factors, and personal responsibilities shape employees' stress levels and overall well-being. Although employees are committed to their duties, their health, morale, and family life are often affected by constant work-related pressures.

The research was based on primary data collected from 80 MESCOM employees through a structured questionnaire, administered both online and offline. The respondents represented different departments and age groups, with a majority belonging to the 26–45 age bracket, where professional responsibilities often overlap with family commitments. Data was analyzed using percentage analysis, graphical tools, and chi-square tests to understand the relationship between demographic factors and work-related stress.

The findings reveal that employees face stress due to long and irregular working hours, shortage of manpower, safety risks, and constant public pressure during outages. These challenges extend beyond the workplace, leading to fatigue, health issues, and strained personal relationships. Lack of recognition, limited career advancement opportunities, and inadequate organizational support further contribute to stress. Despite these hurdles, employees continue to show resilience and dedication in ensuring uninterrupted electricity supply.

The study concludes that stress is not caused by a single factor but by a combination of operational, organizational, and personal challenges. It emphasizes that employee well-being should be treated as a strategic priority, as it directly impacts productivity, safety, and service delivery. Measures such as better manpower planning, shift management, recognition and reward systems, training, and wellness programs are recommended. Addressing stress effectively will not only reduce its negative effects but also create a healthier, more motivated, and future-ready workforce.

Keywords: Work-related stress, MESCOM employees and Employee well-being.

CHAPTER- 1
INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

Work is an essential part of human life, extending far beyond the mere pursuit of financial stability. It defines our identity, shapes our social interactions, and plays a critical role in our mental and emotional well-being. In the contemporary world, the workplace has transformed into an arena of constant challenges, expectations, and deadlines. While technological advancements and modern management practices have improved productivity and efficiency, they have also intensified the pressures faced by employees. One of the most pressing issues arising from this evolving work environment is work-related stress, which has become a major concern for organizations worldwide.

Work-related stress refers to the physical, emotional, or mental strain experienced by employees when the demands of their job exceed their ability to cope effectively. Unlike ordinary stress, which can be temporary and manageable, prolonged exposure to work-related stress can have severe consequences on an individual's health, including anxiety, depression, fatigue, and in extreme cases, burnout. Stress at the workplace does not only affect the employee; it indirectly impacts organizational performance, productivity, and overall morale. Employees who experience high levels of stress may show reduced efficiency, higher absenteeism, and increased likelihood of errors, all of which can affect the organization's goals and service delivery.

Work is basically intertwined with the existence of a human being, as it is not only the source of money and safety but also brings the worker an identity, a social status, and a certain degree of satisfaction. The problem is that nowadays the office or workplace has become a major source of anxiety. The extreme stress at work, resulting from job requirements that go beyond the worker's capacity to deal with the situation properly, has become a whole world problem nowadays. This phenomenon may lead to many negative consequences, such as a decline in physical health, weakening of the mental state, decrease in productivity, and in the end, the quality of life gets worse.

In particular, the electricity industry has always been known for hard work under high tension for many hours, dealing with difficult technical aspects, safety risks, and the need of always being efficient. MESCOM - Mangalore Electricity Supply Company - is central in the supply of electricity to households and industries in the whole state of Karnataka, the Udupi–Manipal region included. The staff of MESCOM is the most susceptible to stressful situations

such as overwork, emergency call outs, long working hours, and public dealing and all these might cohere to both their work performance and well-being.

Such is the importance of knowing the causes and effects of stress among MESCOM employees that the first thing that should be understood is that the problem is not just the employees but also the organization's efficiency and service delivery to consumers. This research work is to analyze the level of work-related stress among MESCOM workers in Udupi–Manipal, to unfold the work factors that lead to stress, and to study the impact of stress on their work and personal life. The study will then present the instruments that will be helpful in the management of stress and for the employee welfare program.

Significance of Studying Work-Related Stress in MESCOM

The study of work-related stress in MESCOM is significant because it highlights the link between employee well-being and organizational performance. Stress does not affect employees in isolation; it also influences productivity, service quality, and operational efficiency. By identifying the key stressors, such as workload, long working hours, emergency duties, and public interactions, organizations can design interventions that reduce stress and improve overall employee satisfaction.

This research focuses on assessing the level of stress among MESCOM employees in the Udupi–Manipal region, identifying the causes and effects of such stress on both work performance and personal life. The study aims to provide insights into the challenges faced by employees and suggest measures to mitigate stress, such as stress management programs, wellness initiatives, employee counseling, and work-life balance strategies. Understanding and managing stress is particularly important in high-risk, high-responsibility sectors like electricity distribution, where the safety and efficiency of operations depend heavily on the alertness and mental well-being of the workforce.

Meaning of Stress

Stress is a human body's normal condition that accompanies a person's feeling of inability to deal with tasks, challenges, or pressure applied by others. Stress is essentially the body's mechanism of responding to a situation that demands one to pay attention, alter the way the thing is done or take action. A little bit of stress at times may prove to be constructive as it makes people to surpass their previous performances. Nevertheless, if the stress is too much

or lasts for a prolonged period of time, the consequent effects are going to be negative on physical health, mental well-being, work performance, and personal life.

On the job, stress is generally caused by the employees' dissatisfaction with the workload in and of itself and the feeling of being out of control of it, the facing of unclarified expectations, or conflicts experienced by them. While the workers of MESCOM are dealing with the stress caused by the long hours of work, emergency duties, the physical dangers, and the pressure from the higher management and the public being placed on them.

Definition

National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH, 1999):

Work stress is defined as “The harmful physical and emotional responses that occur when the requirements of the job do not match the capabilities, resources, or needs of the worker.”

Problem Definition

Stress at work is a major issue in almost all industries around the globe. It impacts the workers not only on a health level but also on moral grounds. This leads to decreased productivity in the company, which is a direct consequence of lost employee engagement. Needless to say, in the electricity sector, where an uninterrupted flow of energy and emergency-like quick solutions are necessities, staff are exposed to situations characterized by unbearable pressure, which consequently results in their facing difficulties to combat stress properly. In contrast to a plethora of office-based jobs, power supply employees are usually subjected to similar stressful situations, for instance, high physical demands, safety risks, irregular working hours, and incessant public pressure to restore power in the shortest possible time in case of power outages. The working class employees of MESCOM (Mangalore Electricity Supply Company) in Udupi–Manipal area are the ones who are subjected to the above-mentioned roles and responsibilities. They have to work in challenging situations practically all the time—power failures are attended to during storms, tech breakdowns are dealt with, they have to climb poles and transformers, and in addition to that, they have to cope with the expectations of the administration as well as the consumers. All these different factors contribute towards a highly stressful working environment. Though their role is very significant, not much is researched about how much stress is experienced by MESCOM workers, the professional performance impact of stress, and the spillover of it into

personal and family life, etc. Many employees usually suffer from stress and keep it to themselves as they do not get enough support from the organizations in terms of counseling, teaching, and having welfare programs. If this problem of stress is ignored for a long time, it becomes primarily responsible for burnout, absenteeism, loss of productivity, accidents, and disease occurrence and development, and finally, aging. Therefore, the issue that this investigation deals with is the absence of a methodical research on the extent and consequences of work-related chronic stress among MESCOM workers in Udupi–Manipal. By recognizing stress sources and levels and impacts, this survey intends to bridge an essential gap in knowledge and give recommendations for the possible intervention that can allow worker health and organization functionality well-to-be.

Why MESCOM Workers Are at Risk of Stress

MESCOM workers are at a higher risk of stress because of the unique and demanding nature of their job. Their work often involves unpredictable situations such as sudden power failures, technical breakdowns, and emergency call-outs at odd hours, which disrupt their daily routines and work–life balance. They are also exposed to high physical risks, including climbing poles, handling live wires, and working in harsh weather conditions, where the possibility of accidents or electrocution is always present. In addition, long and irregular working hours add to their fatigue, while continuous public pressure and consumer expectations for immediate service create emotional strain. Many workers also face challenges of limited staff, inadequate resources, and organizational pressures such as lack of recognition or delayed promotions, which further heighten stress levels. Over time, these factors not only affect their job performance but also spill over into their personal and family life, making MESCOM workers particularly vulnerable to work-related stress.

Statement of the Problem

Work-related stress is a growing challenge across many professions, but MESCOM workers in the Udupi–Manipal region face of stress due to the demanding and risky nature of their jobs. Their responsibilities often involve long and irregular working hours, unpredictable emergencies, and physically hazardous tasks such as repairing power lines under unsafe conditions. In addition, workers deal with public pressure, limited resources, and

organizational challenges, which further intensify their stress levels. Prolonged exposure to such stress not only affects their health and well-being but also reduces job satisfaction, efficiency, and overall service delivery. Despite their crucial role in ensuring uninterrupted electricity supply, there has been limited research into the causes and impacts of stress on MESCOM employees. This study seeks to address this gap by systematically assessing the sources, levels, and consequences of work-related stress among MESCOM workers in Udupi–Manipal.

Background of the Problem

Work-related stress has become one of the most common challenges in today’s world of work. The International Labour Organization (ILO) and the World Health Organization (WHO) describe occupational stress as a growing epidemic that negatively affects employees’ health, organizational efficiency, and even national economies. In India, with its fast-changing work culture and rising public expectations, stress has become a pressing issue in both government and private sectors. Employees are often expected to do more with fewer resources, leading to increasing levels of job strain.

The electricity sector is one of the most stress-prone industries because it directly touches the everyday lives of people. Even a few minutes of power cut can cause frustration among the public, who expect quick solutions. Unlike office-based jobs, electricity workers have to be ready for emergencies at any time, whether it is repairing a line during a heavy downpour, restoring supply in the middle of the night, or handling consumer complaints during peak hours. These situations make their work not only physically demanding but also mentally exhausting.

In coastal Karnataka, MESCOM (Mangalore Electricity Supply Company) workers play a critical role in keeping the region powered. Their daily work involves tasks such as climbing tall poles, fixing broken wires in risky conditions, and attending to sudden breakdowns. For example, during monsoon seasons in Udupi–Manipal, workers are often called out late at night to restore power in storm-hit areas, sometimes standing ankle-deep in water while repairing equipment. Apart from physical dangers, they face constant pressure from the public, who demand immediate service, and from the organization, which expects uninterrupted performance despite limited manpower and resources.

The impact of such stress goes beyond the workplace. Many MESCOM workers struggle to balance their professional duties with family responsibilities. Long working hours, sudden call-outs, and unpredictable shifts often disturb their personal lives, leading to fatigue, strained relationships, and declining health. Yet, despite these visible challenges, very little academic research has been carried out on the stress faced by electricity supply workers. Most existing studies in India focus on IT professionals, teachers, or healthcare staff, leaving a major gap in understanding the struggles of workers in essential public service sectors like electricity distribution.

This study is therefore significant as it aims to highlight the realities of MESCOM workers in Udupi–Manipal, understand the sources and impacts of their stress, and provide recommendations that can help improve their working conditions and overall well-being.

History of MESCOM

The Mangalore Electricity Supply Company Limited (MESCOM) is one of the major electricity distribution companies in Karnataka. It was carved out of the Karnataka Power Transmission Corporation Limited (KPTCL) as part of the power sector reforms initiated by the Government of Karnataka in the late 1990s and early 2000s. These reforms were introduced to improve efficiency, ensure better service to consumers, and decentralize electricity distribution in the state.

MESCOM was officially incorporated in June 2002 as a fully owned Government of Karnataka undertaking under the Companies Act, 1956. Its headquarters is located in Mangalore (Dakshina Kannada district). Over time, MESCOM has grown into a key public utility provider with the mission of ensuring reliable and quality power supply to both urban and rural consumers. Its jurisdiction covers a mix of coastal, hilly, and agricultural regions, which presents unique challenges in power distribution. The company serves more than 20 lakhs (2 million) consumers, including households, industries, businesses, and farmers.

Apart from power distribution, MESCOM has also taken steps to promote energy conservation, rural electrification, and consumer awareness. It has introduced online bill payment systems, grievance redressal mechanisms, and awareness campaigns on safe electricity usage. Despite these initiatives, MESCOM continues to face challenges such as

transmission losses, increasing demand, natural calamities (especially heavy monsoons in coastal Karnataka), and the need for continuous upgradation of infrastructure.

Stress is something that almost everyone experiences in life, but when it becomes a part of everyday work, it turns into a serious problem. For MESCOM workers, stress is not just about meeting deadlines or handling workload in an office — it is about being ready at any moment to climb a pole in heavy rain, repair a snapped line in the middle of the night, or face an angry consumer demanding immediate power restoration. Their job is not only physically tough but also mentally exhausting, as they constantly balance the demands of the public, the expectations of the organization, and their own family responsibilities.

When such stress keeps building up, it affects workers in many ways. It can lead to tiredness, headaches, lack of sleep, or even serious health issues. Emotionally, it may cause frustration, anxiety, or loss of motivation. For many, it also takes away precious family time, leading to strained relationships at home. For MESCOM as an organization, stressed workers mean lower efficiency, more errors, absenteeism, and a higher risk of accidents — which can be dangerous in a field where safety is already a big concern. Consumers too feel the impact, as delays in service or poor communication can cause dissatisfaction and conflicts.

This is why studying stress among MESCOM workers is so important. By understanding what really causes their stress and how it affects their lives, we can look for practical solutions that will make their work safer, healthier, and more fulfilling. At the same time, reducing stress will help MESCOM perform better as an organization and ensure the public receives more reliable electricity service. In short, managing stress is not just about the workers — it is about improving the well-being of families, strengthening the organization, and serving society better.

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Importance of the Study

This study holds great importance because it focuses on the people who work tirelessly behind the scenes to ensure that electricity — a basic necessity of modern life — reaches every home, hospital, shop, school, and industry in the Udupi– Manipal region. Most of the time, society only notices MESCOM workers when there is a power cut, but very few understand the amount of pressure and risk these workers deal with every day. By assessing the stress levels of these employees, this study brings attention to their real challenges and emphasizes the need to support their health and well-being.

For employees, this research is important because it gives them a voice. Many MESCOM workers silently cope with long hours, irregular shifts, hazardous conditions, and public pressure without having an outlet to express their struggles. This study highlights how stress affects not just their work performance but also their family life, social relationships, and overall happiness. By identifying these issues, it can help in designing better support systems such as counseling programs, stress management workshops, or flexible schedules that improve both their mental and physical well-being.

For MESCOM as an organization, the study is equally significant. Stressed workers are more prone to mistakes, accidents, absenteeism, and burnout — all of which reduce efficiency and increase operational costs. By understanding the root causes of employee stress, MESCOM can implement policies that create a healthier work environment. This, in turn, can improve worker motivation, strengthen employee loyalty, and enhance the organization’s reputation as a responsible employer. In the long run, a stress-free and satisfied workforce will ensure smoother operations and higher service quality.

For society and consumers, the importance of this study lies in the direct link between employee well-being and service delivery. When MESCOM workers are overworked and stressed, it leads to delays in addressing power failures, increased risk of accidents, and lower quality of service. On the other hand, when workers feel supported and valued, they can perform their duties more effectively and respond to emergencies with greater confidence and speed. This directly benefits the public, ensuring uninterrupted electricity supply and improved customer satisfaction.

In summary, the importance of this study goes beyond academics. It is about recognizing the human side of electricity distribution — the struggles, sacrifices, and resilience of MESCOM workers. By addressing their stress, we are not only improving their lives but also strengthening the organization and ensuring that society continues to enjoy reliable, safe, and efficient electricity services.

Assessment of Work-Related Stress

Work-related stress is a common challenge in today’s fast-paced world, affecting employees across different professions. It occurs when the demands of a job exceed an individual’s ability to cope, leading to physical, mental, and emotional strain. While a moderate level of stress can sometimes motivate employees to perform better, excessive or prolonged stress can have serious consequences for both the individual and the organization.

For MESCOM workers in Udupi–Manipal, work-related stress is particularly significant. These employees are responsible for ensuring uninterrupted electricity supply to homes, businesses, and public institutions. Their work often involves handling sudden emergencies, repairing power failures during storms, or managing technical breakdowns. Tasks such as

climbing poles, working with live wires, or operating in harsh weather conditions add to their physical and mental strain.

The effects of this stress often extend beyond the workplace. Long hours, night shifts, and unexpected call-outs can disrupt sleep patterns, reduce family time, and affect personal well-being. Over time, this can lower job satisfaction, reduce productivity, and increase the risk of accidents or health issues. Assessing work-related stress among MESCOM workers is therefore essential to understand its causes, measure its impact, and explore ways to improve employee well-being and organizational efficiency, ultimately ensuring better service for the public.

Causes of Work-Related Stress

Work-related stress occurs when employees face pressures that exceed their ability to cope effectively. For MESCOM workers in Udupi–Manipal, stress is caused by a combination of physical, emotional, and organizational challenges. Understanding these causes is important to develop solutions that improve their well-being and efficiency.

1. Unpredictable and Emergency Work

MESCOM workers often respond to sudden power outages, equipment failures, and emergency situations, sometimes in the middle of the night or during harsh weather conditions such as storms and heavy rainfall. This unpredictability makes it hard for them to plan personal time and increases the feeling of constant pressure.

2. Physically Demanding and Risky Tasks

Their job involves climbing poles, handling live wires, and working near high-voltage equipment, often in unsafe or uncomfortable environments. The physical strain combined with the risk of accidents or injuries makes their work extremely stressful, as any small mistake can have serious consequences.

3. Long and Irregular Working Hours

Many MESCOM employees work overtime, night shifts, or during holidays to restore electricity. This disrupts sleep patterns, limits recovery time, and affects family and social life. Chronic fatigue and lack of personal time can accumulate, leading to burnout.

4. Public Pressure and Customer Expectations

Consumers expect electricity to be restored immediately during outages, and frustrated customers often express anger toward frontline workers. Repeated exposure to complaints, criticism, or verbal abuse increases emotional stress and reduces job satisfaction.

5. Limited Resources and Staffing Challenges

Workers often have to complete large workloads with limited manpower or inadequate equipment. This imbalance between job demands and available resources leads to frustration, feelings of helplessness, and decreased motivation.

6. Organizational Pressures

Performance targets, deadlines, bureaucratic procedures, and lack of recognition contribute to stress. Many employees feel undervalued or insecure about their career growth, which affects their mental health and commitment to the organization.

7. Environmental and Climatic Challenges

MESCOM workers frequently work outdoors, exposed to extreme heat, rain, or cold. Such environmental conditions not only increase physical discomfort but also add to stress, especially when combined with urgent repair work during adverse weather.

8. Emotional and Social Factors

Continuous high-pressure work can lead to irritability, anxiety, and frustration. Workers may feel isolated or unsupported if colleagues or supervisors do not provide help or encouragement, intensifying the emotional burden.

9. Impact on Personal and Family Life

Irregular hours, fatigue, and emergency duties often disrupt family routines. Workers may miss important family events, experience strained relationships, and feel guilty for not being able to balance professional and personal responsibilities.

10. Technological and Workload Pressures

With increasing automation, new equipment, and updated procedures, workers need to constantly adapt to technological changes. Combined with growing expectations to handle more tasks efficiently, this creates cognitive overload and stress.

Types of Work-Related Stress

Work-related stress does not affect everyone in the same way. It can be positive, motivating employees to perform better, or negative, causing physical, emotional, and mental problems. Understanding the different types of stress helps organizations and workers manage it more effectively.

1. Eustress (Positive Stress)

Eustress is a type of stress that can actually motivate employees and improve performance. It arises when a challenge feels manageable and encourages focus and effort. For example, a MESCOM worker may experience eustress when assigned to restore a minor power outage. The pressure to complete the task quickly can boost alertness, concentration, and efficiency, leading to a sense of accomplishment once the work is completed.

2. Distress (Negative Stress)

Distress is harmful stress that occurs when job demands exceed an employee's ability to cope. It can result from excessive workload, unsafe working conditions, or repeated emergencies. For MESCOM workers, distress may arise from multiple back-to-back power failures, long night shifts, or constant public complaints. Distress can cause fatigue, anxiety, irritability, and even physical illness if it continues over time.

3. Acute Stress

Acute stress is short-term stress that occurs in response to a specific event or situation. It usually comes suddenly and goes away once the situation is resolved. For example, if a MESCOM worker is called to fix a major transformer breakdown during a storm, the stress is intense but temporary. Acute stress can increase alertness and reaction speed, but frequent episodes without recovery time may lead to emotional exhaustion.

4. Chronic Stress

Chronic stress is long-term stress that results from ongoing pressure and challenging work conditions. For MESCOM employees, chronic stress can develop due to continuous heavy workload, irregular shifts, and lack of adequate rest over months or years. This type of stress can lead to serious health issues such as

hypertension, heart problems, depression, and reduced job satisfaction. Chronic stress also impacts family life, as workers may feel too tired or mentally drained to engage with loved ones.

5. Organizational Stress

This type of stress arises from factors related to the workplace itself, such as unclear job roles, lack of recognition, strict targets, poor management support, or conflicts with colleagues. MESCOM workers may experience organizational stress when they feel their efforts are undervalued or when administrative pressures make daily tasks more difficult.

6. Environmental Stress

Environmental stress is caused by external conditions such as extreme weather, noise, or hazardous work environments. For MESCOM workers, climbing poles in the scorching sun, repairing lines in heavy rain, or working near high-voltage equipment adds to both physical and mental stress.

Background of MESCOM and Its Work Environment

MESCOM was established in 2002 after the unbundling of the Karnataka Electricity Board, with the objective of improving the efficiency of electricity distribution and ensuring reliable power supply across its service regions. The company is tasked with supplying electricity to a varied population, including urban and rural households, commercial enterprises, and industrial units. The nature of work in MESCOM requires employees to deal with technical, operational, and administrative challenges simultaneously.

The employees' responsibilities are diverse and include maintenance of electricity lines, prompt response to outages, handling complaints from consumers, and performing preventive maintenance to avoid system failures. These tasks are often performed under tight schedules and sometimes in adverse conditions, such as during storms or power failures. Emergency call-outs and overtime work are common, and employees are expected to remain vigilant and efficient while managing safety protocols. Moreover, the public interaction aspect of the job adds another layer of stress, as employees must maintain professionalism and provide satisfactory service under pressure.

The organizational structure of MESCOM, like many utility companies, emphasizes efficiency, accountability, and technical competence. While this is essential for maintaining

uninterrupted power supply, it can inadvertently contribute to heightened stress among employees if workload, time pressure, and role expectations are not balanced with adequate support systems. Additionally, technological advancements and increasing consumer expectations have created new challenges, requiring continuous skill development and adaptation, which can further strain employees.

CHAPTER-2
LITERATURE REVIEW

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. **Schaubroeck, J., Ganster, D., & Fox, M. (1992).** This study focused on how an individual's emotional disposition influences stress at work. People with negative emotions were more likely to perceive situations as stressful, while those with positive emotions showed better coping abilities. The findings suggest that stress is not solely caused by external factors but is also shaped by personality traits. Organizations can improve employee resilience by providing emotional support, training, and promoting positive workplace culture.
2. **Von Onciul, J. (1996).** Von Onciul examined stress as a common workplace disorder. Stress results from long working hours, high workload, lack of autonomy, and insufficient managerial support. It leads to both physical problems, like headaches and heart conditions, and psychological issues, such as anxiety and depression. The study emphasized early identification and implementation of preventive strategies to minimize negative health impacts and maintain employee productivity.
3. **Triplett, R., Mullings, J. L., & Scarborough, K. E. (1999).** This research highlighted the stress caused by conflicts between work responsibilities and personal life. Correctional officers who struggled to balance work and home life experienced higher stress levels, fatigue, and job dissatisfaction. The study stressed the importance of flexible scheduling, supportive policies, and programs to reduce work-home conflicts, improving both employee health and organizational efficiency.
4. **Holmes, S. (2001).** Holmes provided a concise review of work-related stress, noting major causes such as heavy workload, poor role clarity, lack of control, and inadequate support. Stress was linked to decreased productivity, mental health issues like anxiety and depression, and physical health concerns. The study emphasized that organizations should proactively create healthier workplaces and provide supportive environments to reduce stress.
5. **Tennant, C. (2001).** Tennant studied the connection between work stress and depression. High levels of stress from heavy workload, lack of support, and low job control significantly increased the risk of depressive disorders. The research highlighted the importance of recognizing early symptoms and implementing workplace interventions to safeguard employees' mental health.

6. **Cox, T., & Rial-Gonzalez, E. (2002).** This study examined stress across European workplaces, finding that high workloads, job insecurity, tight deadlines, and lack of support were common stressors. Stress led to physical health issues, decreased productivity, and increased absenteeism. The authors emphasized the need for preventive workplace measures, better working conditions, and strong support systems to protect employee health and improve organizational performance.
7. **Shirom, A. (2003).** Shirom investigated the short- and long-term health consequences of work stress. Chronic stress was linked to fatigue, burnout, weakened immunity, heart problems, anxiety, and depression. Stress also negatively affected productivity and job satisfaction, underscoring that employee health and organizational outcomes are closely linked.
8. **Weibel, L., Gabrion, I., Aussedat, M., & Kreutz, G. (2003).** This study highlighted the intense stress experienced by emergency medical dispatchers. High workloads and emotionally demanding tasks led to fatigue, errors, and psychological strain. Organizational support and stress management interventions were recommended to reduce risks and improve employee well-being.
9. **Cousins, R., Mackay, C. J., Clarke, S. D., Kelly, C., Kelly, P. J., & Mc Caig, R. H. (2004).** The study focused on practical tools and standards to manage workplace stress in the UK. By addressing workload, role clarity, and managerial support, organizations could detect stress early and implement preventive strategies. Structured approaches helped organizations meet legal responsibilities while improving employee well-being.
10. **Dahlgren, A., Kecklund, G., & Akerstedt, T. (2005).** This study demonstrated that higher stress levels lead to poor sleep, daytime fatigue, and elevated cortisol levels, a stress hormone. The research confirmed that chronic stress negatively impacts both physical and mental health. Stress management strategies are crucial to protect employees' overall well-being.
11. **Johnson, S., Cooper, C., Cartwright, S., Donald, I., Taylor, P., & Millet, C. (2005).** Stress was shown to be common across occupations but varied by job type. Healthcare workers and teachers faced emotional demands, whereas managers dealt with high responsibility and long hours. The study emphasized tailoring stress reduction strategies to specific occupational challenges to improve productivity and satisfaction.
12. **Blaug, R., Kenyon, A., & Lekhi, R. (2007).** This study explored common causes of workplace stress, including high workloads, tight deadlines, lack of control, and insufficient managerial support. Stress was linked to physical issues such as fatigue and

illness, as well as mental problems like anxiety, low motivation, and burnout. The research emphasized that stressed employees are less productive and more prone to absenteeism. It highlighted the importance of creating supportive work environments, promoting work-life balance, and implementing stress management programs to improve both employee well-being and organizational efficiency.

- 13. Cox, T., Griffiths, A., & Rial, E. (2010).** The study explained that work-related stress arises from heavy workloads, poor communication, lack of control, and insufficient managerial support. Stress affects both physical and mental health, leading to fatigue, illness, anxiety, and depression. Additionally, it reduces productivity and job satisfaction. The authors emphasized prevention through better work design, stress management programs, and promoting employee well-being, making it clear that stress management benefits both employees and organizations.
- 14. Nakao, M. (2010).** This research focused on the connection between stress, the mind, and the body. Work-related stress was shown to cause headaches, high blood pressure, heart problems, and mental health issues like anxiety and depression. Early intervention and workplace support were recommended to reduce these risks and protect both physical and psychological health.
- 15. Rowden, P., Matthews, G., Watson, B., & Biggs, H. (2011).** This study highlighted that work-related stress carries over into other life domains, such as driving. Employees experiencing high work stress were more likely to drive carelessly or become fatigued, increasing accident risk. It showed that stress affects not just the workplace but also safety and behavior in daily life, emphasizing the need for holistic stress management.
- 16. Hauke, A., Flintrop, J., Brun, E., & Rugulies, R. (2011).** This review linked high job demands, poor control, and low social support to musculoskeletal pain in areas like the neck, shoulders, and back. Stress was identified as a contributor to physical illness, showing that psychosocial stressors have both mental and bodily consequences. The study emphasized workplace interventions to prevent long-term health problems.
- 17. Elci, M., Şener, I., Aksoy, S., & Alpkın, L. (2012).** This study found that ethical and effective leadership reduces employee stress and turnover intentions. Poor leadership increases stress, causing dissatisfaction and a higher likelihood of leaving the organization. The research highlighted that leadership style not only affects stress levels but also retention and overall workplace satisfaction.

- 18. Lee, J. S., Joo, E. J., & Choi, K. S. (2013).** This study revealed that work stress affects depression indirectly by lowering self-esteem and increasing perceived pressure. Stress does not act in isolation; emotional factors such as confidence and self-worth play a crucial role. Stress management programs that boost self-esteem can protect employees' mental health and well-being.
- 19. Rauschenbach, C., Krumm, S., Thielgen, M., & Hertel, G. (2013)..** The research showed that younger and older employees experience stress differently. Younger workers are stressed by career development pressures, while older employees may face challenges from changing job demands and health issues. Age-specific support and interventions were recommended to improve employee well-being and performance across all career stages.
- 20. Greenhaus, J. H., & Parasuraman, S. (2014).** This study explored how stress at work and outside work interact. Stress in one area can spill over into another, affecting overall life satisfaction and performance. The findings emphasized that stress management should address both work and non-work pressures, helping employees achieve better balance and well-being.
- 21. Giorgi, G., Arcangeli, G., Perminiene, M., Lorini, C., Ariza-Montes, A., Fiz-Perez, J., ... & Mucci, N. (2017).** This study focused on stress in the banking sector, caused by long hours, heavy workloads, performance targets, and job insecurity. High stress levels led to burnout, health problems, reduced job satisfaction, and poor performance. The research highlighted the organizational responsibility to create healthier environments and manage stress proactively.
- 22. Hassard, J., Teoh, K. R., Visockaite, G., Dewe, P., & Cox, T. (2018).** This systematic review showed that work stress has significant social and economic costs. Stress leads to absenteeism, reduced productivity, and higher healthcare expenses. The study emphasized that managing stress is crucial not only for employee health but also for organizational efficiency and societal welfare.
- 23. Asaloei, S. I., Wolomasi, A. K., & Werang, B. R. (2020).** This study found that stress in teachers, caused by heavy workloads, large class sizes, and administrative tasks, reduces teaching effectiveness and negatively impacts mental and physical health. Stress management, support policies, and resources were emphasized to maintain both teacher well-being and student learning outcomes.
- 24. Schoger, L. I. (2025).** This recent study examined whether education and training help employees cope with stress. Findings suggested that educational programs can improve

knowledge, resilience, and stress management skills. Organizations that invest in employee development may reduce stress-related issues and improve overall workplace health and performance.

Research Gap

Work-related stress has been widely studied across various sectors globally, with research highlighting its causes, effects, and management strategies. Numerous studies have focused on stress among employees in IT, healthcare, manufacturing, and banking sectors, providing valuable insights into the dynamics of workplace stress, coping mechanisms, and organizational interventions. However, despite the critical role of utility service providers in society, research specifically addressing the stress levels of employees in electricity distribution companies remains limited.

In the context of India, while large-scale organizations have occasionally been studied, regional electricity companies like MESCOM have received very little attention in academic research. Most existing literature tends to focus on urban or corporate workplaces, leaving a significant gap in understanding the challenges faced by employees in essential service organizations, particularly in smaller towns and semi-urban regions such as Udupi. The work environment in such organizations is distinct: employees often face unpredictable workload fluctuations, field duties under harsh conditions, safety risks, and direct interactions with consumers, which differ substantially from stressors in conventional office-based jobs.

CHAPTER-3
RESEARCH DESIGN

RESEARCH DESIGN

RESEARCH

Research is a systematic and detailed study of a specific problem, subject, or area of interest. It involves collecting, compiling, and analyzing information to gain better understanding and provide solutions. In simple words, research is a scientific investigation carried out to discover new knowledge or insights. According to the Advanced Learner’s Dictionary of Current English, research is described as a careful and thorough inquiry aimed at finding new facts in any field of knowledge.

NEED FOR STUDY

Work is a central part of human life, but when demands at the workplace exceed the worker’s ability to cope, stress arises. In organizations like MESCOM, which provides essential electricity services, employees often face heavy workloads, irregular schedules, public pressure, and limited resources. Such stress not only affects their health and well-being but also reduces efficiency and service quality.

Understanding the causes and impact of stress on MESCOM workers in Udupi–Manipal is important because their roles directly influence public service delivery. By studying stress patterns and their effects, we can recommend strategies for stress management, better employee welfare, and improved organizational productivity.

This study fills a research gap, as very few studies have focused specifically on the stress faced by MESCOM employees in this region. The findings will help management, policymakers, and workers themselves in addressing stress-related challenges.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To analyze the demographic profile of MESCOM workers (age, gender, marital status, education, job role, and years of service) and understand how these factors relate to work-related stress.
2. To identify the level and frequency of stress experienced by MESCOM workers due to job responsibilities, workload, and organizational demands

3. To examine the main sources of stress at work such as long working hours, lack of staff, deadlines, physical workload, recognition, and communication issues
4. To assess the impact of stress on employee well-being in terms of physical symptoms (fatigue, headaches, body pain) and mental exhaustion.
5. To evaluate how work stress affects personal and family life as well as employees' work-life balance and job performance.
6. To study the coping mechanisms adopted by MESCOM workers (taking breaks, exercise, meditation, talking to colleagues/family, or ignoring stress)..

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This project focuses on 80 MESCOM employees working in the Udupi–Manipal region. The study tries to understand what causes stress at work and how it affects their health, family life, and job performance. Issues like workload, long hours, safety risks, emergencies, and organizational pressures are taken into account. The study also looks at whether age, gender, experience, or job role make a difference in stress levels. The findings will help suggest ways to reduce stress and improve employee well-being.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a descriptive and analytical approach. A total of 80 MESCOM employees were selected from different departments and job roles in Udupi–Manipal. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire, shared both online and in person. To make sure all groups were included fairly, stratified random sampling was used. Primary data was collected directly from workers, while secondary information was taken from journals, reports, and books. The collected data was analyzed using Excel with tools like percentages, averages, and chi-square tests

SOURCE OF DATA

The study is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data comes directly from 80 MESCOM employees through a questionnaire that included questions on their personal profile, work conditions, and sources of stress. Secondary data comes from books, journals,

earlier studies,. Together, these sources give a complete picture of stress faced by workers and its impact on their lives and performance

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study follows a descriptive survey design. A total of 80 MESCOM employees were chosen from the Udupi–Manipal region, covering both technical and administrative roles. Stratified random sampling was used so that all categories of workers were represented fairly. A structured questionnaire with multiple-choice and The responses were analyzed using Excel with simple statistical methods such as percentages, averages, and chi-square tests. The research is limited to MESCOM employees in Udupi–Manipal.

SAMPLE PLAN

The study was carried out among MESCOM employees working in the Udupi–Manipal region. Workers from different departments such as technical staff, field workers, and office staff were included to ensure fair coverage. The idea behind the sample plan was to capture a balanced view of stress across all job roles. Both online and printed questionnaires were used, making it possible to reach employees effectively and gather genuine information about their work-related stress.

SAMPLE SIZE

The sample size for this project was fixed at 80 employees. This number was considered appropriate as it covered staff from various departments and roles without being too large to manage. By including 80 workers, the study could highlight the main causes and impacts of stress while still remaining practical within the available time and resources. This sample provided enough data to study patterns of stress among MESCOM employees in Udupi–Manipal.

SAMPLE METHOD

To select employees fairly, the study used a stratified random sampling method. Workers were first grouped into categories like field staff, technical staff, and office staff. From each group, individuals were chosen randomly. This ensured that every department was

represented and that the results were not biased toward any single category of workers. This method gave a clear picture of how stress affects people in different roles within MESCOM.

CHI-SQUARE TEST

The Chi-square test was used to examine whether factors like age, gender, marital status, education, and years of service had any link with stress levels. It helped check if differences in stress were due to real reasons or just random variation. This test provided scientific support for the study's findings and helped confirm or reject the research hypotheses with confidence.

The formula for the chi-square test is:

$$\chi^2 = \sum (\mathbf{O} - \mathbf{E})^2 / \mathbf{E}$$

Where:

- χ^2 = Chi-square value
- \mathbf{O} = Observed frequency (the actual responses collected)
- \mathbf{E} = Expected frequency (the values calculated assuming no relationship)

If the difference between observed and expected values is small, the chi-square result will also be small, showing no strong relationship. But if the difference is large, the chi-square value will be high, which may mean the two variables are significantly related.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

1. Responses were self-reported, which might include bias.
2. Stress is a personal and subjective experience, making it hard to measure with full accuracy.
3. Limited time and resources prevented deeper or long-term analysis.
4. The study only looked at current stress levels, not long-term impacts on career or health.

CHAPTER-4

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Table Showing Age Distribution of the Respondents

Particular	No. of Response	Percentage
Below 25	5	6%
26–35	27	34%
36–45	35	44%
46and above	13	16%
Total	80	100 %

4.1 Chart Showing Age Distribution of the Respondents

INTERPRETATION

The age distribution of MESCOM workers surveyed shows a diverse range, with the majority falling between 26 and 45 years old. Specifically, 44% of respondents are aged 36 to 45, indicating a relatively experienced workforce in their mid-career phase. The next largest group is the 26 to 35 age bracket, comprising 34%, which suggests a significant number of younger, possibly newer employees bringing fresh energy to the organization. Workers below 25 make up only 6%, indicating that MESCOM has relatively few very young or entry-level staff in this sample. Finally, 16% are aged 46 and above, representing the senior or veteran employees who likely bring valuable expertise and institutional knowledge. This distribution highlights a workforce that is mostly in their prime working years, balancing both experience and youthful vigor. Understanding this age mix is important, as stress levels and coping mechanisms may vary across age groups, influencing the overall impact of work-related stress on MESCOM employees.

4.2 Table showing the Gender of the Respondents .

Particular	No. of Response	Percentage %
Male	70	88%
Female	10	13%
Other	0	0%
Total	80	100%

4.2 Chart showing the Gender of the Respondents

INTERPRETATION

The gender distribution of MESCOM workers in Udupi-Manipal is heavily male-dominated, with 88% of respondents being men and only 13% women. This reflects the traditionally male-skewed workforce in technical and field-related roles in the power sector. While male employees may face physical workload stress, female employees, though fewer in number, may encounter unique challenges such as work-life balance, underrepresentation, or lack of gender-sensitive infrastructure. The absence of respondents identifying as "Other" indicates minimal or no gender diversity beyond the binary. Addressing stress effectively requires acknowledging these gender-based differences and creating a more inclusive, supportive work environment for all.

4.3. Table showing Marital Status of the Respondents

Particular	No. of Response	Percentage
Unmarried	35	44%
Married	45	56%
Other	0	0%
Total	80	100%

4.3. Chart showing Marital Status of the Respondents

INTERPRETATION

The survey results show that 56% of MESCOM workers in Udupi-Manipal are married, while 44% are unmarried. This balanced mix reflects a workforce that includes both individuals with family responsibilities and those in earlier stages of life or career. Married employees may experience higher stress due to the pressure of balancing work with family obligations, especially in demanding roles with long hours or emergency duties. Unmarried workers, though possibly more flexible, may still face stress from job uncertainty or lack of personal time. Understanding these dynamics helps in planning support systems tailored to personal life situations and stress triggers

4.4. Table showing Educational Qualification of the Respondents

SSLC	7	9%
PUC	17	21%
Diploma	19	24%
Postgraduate	7	9%
Graduate	28	35%
Engineering	2	3%
Total	80	100%

4.4. Chart showing Educational Qualification of the Respondents

INTERPRETATION

The educational profile of MESCOM workers in Udupi-Manipal shows that the majority (35%) are graduates, indicating a reasonably well-educated workforce. A significant portion also hold diplomas (24%) and PUC qualifications (21%), reflecting a mix of technical and academic backgrounds suited for operational and field roles. Only 3% are engineers, suggesting that most high-level technical tasks may be centralized or outsourced. Interestingly, 9% of workers have only SSLC-level education, indicating reliance on field experience over formal education in some roles. This diverse mix highlights the need for stress management programs that consider both educational and skill-level differences among staff.

4.5. Table Showing Job Role of Responds in MESCOM

Particular	No. of response	percentage
Line Man	41	51%
Field Staff	9	11%
Office Staff	17	21%
Supervisor	12	15%
Assistant accounts officer	1	1%
Total	80	100%

4.5. Chart Showing Job Role of Respond in MESCO

INTERPRETATION

The job role distribution shows that a majority (51%) of MESCOM employees in Udupi-Manipal are linemen, who are directly involved in physically demanding fieldwork such as power line maintenance and repairs. This role often involves high risk, irregular hours, and exposure to harsh weather—making them more vulnerable to stress and fatigue. Office staff (21%) and supervisors (15%) contribute to administrative and oversight functions, which may involve pressure related to coordination and reporting. Field staff (11%) also work on the ground, while only 1% are in accounts-related roles. Each role comes with unique stress factors that must be addressed differently.

4.6. Table Showing Year of Service of Respondents in MESCOM

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Less than 1 year	6	8%
1-3 years	18	23%
4-6 years	11	14%
Above 6 years	45	56%
Total	80	100%

4.6. Chart Showing Year of Service of Respondents in MESCOM

INTERPRETATION

The data shows that more than half of the MESCOM workers surveyed (56%) have over six years of service, highlighting a highly experienced and stable workforce. These long-serving employees likely possess deep technical knowledge and familiarity with field challenges, but may also be more vulnerable to chronic stress or physical fatigue. Meanwhile, 23% have 1–3 years of experience, and 14% fall in the 4–6 year range—this group may be balancing learning curves with growing responsibilities. Only 8% are newcomers (less than a year), showing low recent recruitment. Overall, support programs should address both seasoned and newer employees' unique stress profiles

4.7. Table Showing Stress Levels of Respondents Based on Job Responsibilities

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Always	6	8%
Often	6	8%
Sometimes	56	70%
Rarely	10	13%
Never	2	3%
Total	80	100%

4.7. Chart Showing Stress Levels of Respondents Based on Job Responsibilities

INTERPRETATION

The majority of MESCOM workers (70%) reported feeling stressed sometimes due to their job responsibilities, reflecting the demanding and unpredictable nature of their work. A smaller but significant number (16%) feel stressed always or often, indicating a group that may be at risk for chronic stress and burnout. Meanwhile, 13% feel stressed rarely, and only 3% report never experiencing stress. This shows that while stress is common among workers, its intensity varies widely. These insights highlight the need for flexible support systems that can help workers manage stress based on its frequency and impact.

4.8. Table Showing Major Sources of Stress Among Respondents

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Long working hours	11	8%
Dealing with customers/public pressure	10	7%
Lack of staff	54	39%
Deadlines and targets	25	18%
Physical workload	19	14%
Lack of recognition	10	7%
Poor communication from management	8	6%
Total	137	100%

4.8. Chart Showing Major Sources of Stress Among Respondents

INTERPRETATION

Among MESCOM workers in Udupi- Manipal, the biggest source of stress is lack of staff, affecting 39% of respondents. This understaffing likely increases workload and pressure on existing employees. The second major factor is deadlines and targets (18%), showing the stress caused by performance expectations. Physical workload also contributes (14%), reflecting the demanding nature of field duties. Other notable stressors include long working hours (8%), public pressure (7%), and lack of recognition (7%). Additionally, poor communication from management (6%) adds to the stress, highlighting the need for improved support and clearer workplace communication.

4.9. Table Showing Perception of Workload Among Respondents

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Very high	4	5%
High	34	43%
Moderate	41	51%
Low	1	1%
Very low	0	0%
Total	80	100%

4.9. Chart Showing Perception of Workload Among Respondents

INTERPRETATION

Most MESCOM workers in Udupi-Manipal describe their workload as moderate (51%), suggesting a generally manageable level of daily tasks for over half the workforce. However, a significant portion (43%) feel their workload is high, which may contribute to elevated stress levels, fatigue, and decreased job satisfaction. A small minority (5%) experience a very high workload, likely placing them at risk for burnout if support isn't provided. Only 1% report a low workload, indicating few employees feel underutilized. This distribution highlights the importance of balancing task allocation to prevent overload while maintaining productivity.

4.10. Table Showing Clarity of Communication from Supervisors

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Yes	46	58%
No	18	23%
Sometimes	16	20%
Total	80	100%

4.10. Chart Showing Clarity of Communication from Supervisors

INTERPRETATION

A majority of MESCOM workers (58%) in Udupi- Manipal report receiving clear instructions and communication from their supervisors, which is essential for smooth workflow and reducing job-related stress. However, nearly a quarter (23%) feel they do not receive clear guidance, while 20% say communication is only sometimes clear. This inconsistency can lead to confusion, errors, and frustration among employees, contributing to stress and reduced productivity. Strengthening communication channels and ensuring regular, transparent instructions from supervisors can greatly improve employee confidence and overall job satisfaction.

4.11. Table Showing Frequency of Physical Symptoms of Stress Among Respondents

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Daily	5	6%
Weekly	7	9%
Monthly	19	24%
Rarely	45	56%
Never	4	5%
Total	80	100%

4.11. Chart Showing Frequency of Physical Symptoms of Stress Among Respondents

INTERPRETATION

Among MESCOM workers in Udupi-Manipal, over half (56%) experience physical symptoms of stress such as fatigue, headaches, or body pain rarely, indicating that many manage stress well or have coping mechanisms in place. However, 24% report these symptoms monthly, while 9% experience them weekly, and 6% face them daily—showing a significant portion dealing with ongoing physical stress impacts. A small 5% report never experiencing such symptoms. This data suggests that while most workers cope adequately, targeted health and wellness programs could help those regularly affected by physical stress symptoms.

4.12. Table Showing Frequency of Mental Exhaustion Among Respondent

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Always	4	5%
Often	8	10%
Sometimes	55	69%
Rarely	10	13%
Never	3	4%
Total	80	100%

4.12. Chart Showing Frequency of Mental Exhaustion Among Respondent

INTERPRETATION

Most MESCOM workers (69%) in Udupi-Manipal feel mentally exhausted sometimes after work, reflecting the mentally demanding nature of their roles. Additionally, 15% experience mental exhaustion often or always, indicating a notable group at risk of burnout or decreased well-being if stress isn't managed. Meanwhile, 13% feel exhausted rarely, and only 4% never face mental fatigue, suggesting that a small portion manage to maintain good mental energy. These results emphasize the importance of mental health support, such as stress-relief programs and workload management, to improve employee resilience and productivity.

4.13. Table Showing Impact of Job on Personal/Family Life of Respondents

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Yes	14	18%
No	47	59%
Sometimes	19	24%
Total	80	100%

4.13. Chart Showing Impact of Job on Personal/Family Life of Respondents

INTERPRETATION

For MESCOM workers in Udupi-Manipal, 59% reported that their job does not affect their personal or family life, suggesting that many can balance work and home responsibilities effectively. However, 18% feel that their job does impact their personal or family life, while another 24% say it sometimes does. This highlights that nearly half of the workforce experiences some level of interference from work demands, possibly due to irregular hours, stress, or workload. Addressing this through flexible scheduling or family-friendly policies could improve overall well-being and job satisfaction.

4.14. Table Showing Respondents’ Perception of Unrealistic Work Expectations

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Yes	21	26%
No	24	30%
Occasionally	35	44%
Total	80	100%

4.14. Chart Showing Respondents’ Perception of Unrealistic Work Expectations

INTERPRETATION

Among MESCOM workers in Udupi-Manipal, 26% feel consistent pressure to meet unrealistic expectations or targets, which can contribute significantly to job stress and burnout. Meanwhile, 44% experience this pressure occasionally, indicating that many face fluctuating demands that may cause intermittent stress. Only 30% report no such pressure, suggesting that unrealistic expectations affect a majority of the workforce at some level. This highlights the need for realistic goal-setting and better workload management to reduce undue stress and promote a healthier work environment.

4.15. Table Showing Satisfaction with Work-Life Balance of Respondents

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Very Satisfied	5	6%
Satisfied	29	36%
Neutral	39	49%
Dissatisfied	6	8%
Very Dissatisfied	1	1%
Total	80	100%

4.15. Chart Showing Satisfaction with Work-Life Balance of Respondents

INTERPRETATION

Among MESCOM workers in Udupi-Manipal, only 42% (6% very satisfied, 36% satisfied) feel positive about their current work-life balance, indicating room for improvement. Nearly half (49%) remain neutral, suggesting ambivalence or uncertainty about how well they manage work and personal life. Meanwhile, 9% feel dissatisfied or very dissatisfied, pointing to a smaller group struggling with balancing demands. This mixed response highlights the need for targeted initiatives like flexible hours, stress management, and support programs to enhance overall satisfaction and employee well-being.

4.16. Table Showing Impact of Stress on Job Performance of Respondents

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Yes	29	36%
No	38	48%
Not sure	13	16%
Total	80	100%

4.16. Chart Showing Impact of Stress on Job Performance of Respondents

INTERPRETATION

Among MESCOM workers in Udupi-Manipal, 36% believe that stress negatively affects their job performance, highlighting a substantial portion of employees who recognize the toll stress takes on their productivity and focus. Meanwhile, 48% feel that stress does not impact their work, which could reflect strong coping skills or resilience. Another 16% are unsure, suggesting some ambiguity or varying effects of stress depending on circumstances. This data underscores the importance of stress management initiatives to help those affected maintain high performance and job satisfaction.

4.17. Table Showing Stress Management Techniques Adopted by Respondents

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Talking to colleagues or family	13	15%
Taking breaks	32	38%
Yoga or meditation	4	5%
Exercise or sports	20	24%
Ignore it / Don't cope actively	16	19%
Total	85	100%

4.17. Chart Showing Stress Management Techniques Adopted by Respondents

INTERPRETATION

MESCOM workers in Udupi-Manipal use various methods to manage stress. The most common approach is taking breaks (38%), which helps employees momentarily step away from stressful tasks and recharge. Exercise or sports also play a significant role (24%), promoting physical health and mental well-being. Some workers (15%) find relief through talking to colleagues or family, emphasizing the importance of social support. However, 19% admit to ignoring stress or not actively coping, which could lead to long-term negative effects. A smaller group (5%) practices yoga or meditation, highlighting opportunities to encourage mindfulness practices.

4.18. Table Showing Availability of Stress Support Programs in MESCOM

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Yes	25	31%
No	38	48%
Not aware	17	21%
Total	80	100%

4.18. Chart Showing Availability of Stress Support Programs in MESCOM

INTERPRETATION

Only 31% of MESCOM workers in Udupi-Manipal are aware that the organization provides stress support measures like counseling, seminars, or welfare programs. Alarmingly, 48% say that no such support is provided, while 21% are not aware of whether it exists—indicating poor communication or lack of visibility of such initiatives. This suggests a critical gap in employee wellness efforts. Even if some programs exist, they may not be effectively reaching or engaging staff. There’s a clear need for MESCOM to not only introduce or strengthen support systems, but also actively promote them across all departments.

4.19. Table Showing Respondents' Comfort in Discussing Stress with Supervisors

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Yes	34	43%
No	20	25%
Not sure	26	33%
Total	80	100%

4.19. Chart Showing Respondents' Comfort in Discussing Stress with Supervisors

INTERPRETATION

Only 43% of MESCOM workers in Udupi-Manipal feel comfortable discussing work-related stress with their manager or supervisor. This means that more than half either feel uncomfortable (25%) or are unsure (33%), which indicates a gap in trust or openness in the workplace environment. When employees don't feel safe sharing their concerns, stress may go unaddressed, leading to burnout and decreased performance. This highlights the importance of building a more supportive and approachable management culture where open communication is encouraged and employees feel heard without fear of judgment or consequences.

4.20. Table Showing Participation of Respondents in Stress Management Training/Workshops

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Yes	19	24%
No	30	38%
Not aware	31	39%
Total	80	100%

4.20.Chart Showing Participation of Respondents in Stress Management Training/Workshops

INTERPRETATION

Only 24% of MESCOM employees in Udupi-Manipal have received stress management training or attended related workshops, indicating limited organizational focus on proactive mental wellness. Surprisingly, 39% are not even aware of such programs, which reflects poor communication or lack of visibility. Meanwhile, 38% confirmed they have not received any training. This highlights a clear need for MESCOM to either introduce or enhance training programs, and more importantly, ensure all staff are aware and encouraged to participate. Promoting mental wellness through structured training can significantly improve employee resilience, morale, and long-term productivity.

4.21. Table Showing Perception of Management’s Concern for Employee Well-Being

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Strongly Agree	5	6%
Agree	18	23%
Neutral	51	64%
Disagree	5	6%
Strongly Disagree	1	1%
Total	80	100%

4.21. Chart Showing Perception of Management’s Concern for Employee Well-Being

INTERPRETATION

A large majority of MESCOM employees in Udupi-Manipal (64%) feel neutral about whether management is concerned about their well-being, which suggests uncertainty or lack of visible efforts from leadership. Only 29% express a positive view (6% strongly agree, 23% agree)—a modest level of confidence in management's commitment to employee welfare. Meanwhile, 7% disagree or strongly disagree. This indicates a need for MESCOM to demonstrate more transparent and consistent efforts in supporting worker well-being through open dialogue, wellness initiatives, and responsive management practices to build greater trust and engagement.

4. 22 What do you think MESCOM can do to reduce employee stress?

MESCOM employees suggest a range of improvements to reduce workplace stress. Many emphasize the need for better staffing to reduce workload, along with realistic targets and clear communication from management. There is a desire for more frequent breaks, flexible scheduling, and health and wellness programs such as counseling, stress management workshops, and physical fitness initiatives. Some also highlight the importance of recognition and appreciation for their efforts. Overall, workers want a more supportive and balanced work environment, where their well-being is considered as important as performance.

4.23. Table Showing Respondents’ Recommendations for Stress-Related Training/Wellness Sessions

Particular	No. of response	Percentage
Yes	21	26%
No	17	21%
Maybe	42	53%
Total	80	100%

4.23. Chart Showing Respondents’ Recommendations for Stress-Related Training/Wellness Sessions

INTERPRETATION

When asked about recommending stress-related training or wellness sessions, 26% of MESCOM employees gave a clear “Yes”, reflecting genuine interest in mental health support. A larger group, 53%, responded with “Maybe”, suggesting they are open to the idea but may want more clarity on the content or benefits of such programs. Meanwhile, 21% responded “No”, possibly due to skepticism or lack of awareness. This shows that while there’s moderate enthusiasm, there’s also a need to build awareness, reduce stigma, and communicate the value of wellness programs to encourage broader participation.

4.24 Any additional comments or suggestions?

In their final comments, MESCOM employees shared thoughtful suggestions for improving their work environment. Common themes included calls for more staff recruitment, better communication from leadership, and regular recognition of employee efforts. Some employees expressed the need for improved facilities, updated safety equipment, and transparent promotion policies. A few highlighted the importance of organizing wellness programs, team-building activities, and providing mental health support. These comments reflect a genuine desire for a more balanced, respectful, and employee-friendly workplace. If addressed, these insights can serve as a strong foundation for creating a healthier and more productive organizational culture.

4.25. Chi-Square Test between Age And Stress due to job responsibilities

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant association between the age of MESCOM workers and the level of stress due to job responsibilities.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): There is a significant association between the age of MESCOM workers and the level of stress due to job responsibilities.

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Age level of the Respondents * Stress level of the Respondents	80	100.0%	0	0.0%	80	100.0%

Age level of the Respondents * Stress level of the Respondents Cross tabulation

			Stress level of the Respondents					Total
			Alw ays	Ofte n	Somet imes	Rar ely	Nev er	
Age level of the Respondents	below 25	Count	1	0	3	1	0	5
		Expecte d Count	.4	.4	3.5	.6	.1	5.0
	26-35	Count	1	4	19	2	1	27
		Expecte d Count	2.0	2.0	18.9	3.4	.7	27.0
	36-45	Count	4	1	26	4	0	35
		Expecte d Count	2.6	2.6	24.5	4.4	.9	35.0
46 and above	Count	0	1	8	3	1	13	
	Expecte d Count	1.0	1.0	9.1	1.6	.3	13.0	
Total		Count	6	6	56	10	2	80
		Expecte d Count	6.0	6.0	56.0	10.0	2.0	80.0

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.400 ^a	12	.495
Likelihood Ratio	12.634	12	.396
N of Valid Cases	80		

a. 17 cells (85.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .13.

Results (Chi-Square Test)

The Chi-Square test was conducted to examine the relationship between the selected variables. The results showed a Pearson Chi-Square value of 11.400 with 12 degrees of freedom and a significance level (p-value) of 0.495. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis could not be rejected.

Interpretation

This indicates that there is no statistically significant association between the two variables under study. In other words, the variables appear to be independent of each other in the present sample. However, as 85% of the cells had expected counts less than 5, the reliability of this result may be limited.

4.26. Chi-Square Test between Job Role in MESCOM And Do you feel stressed due to your job responsibilities?

- **Null Hypothesis (H₀)** : There is no significant association between the job role of MESCOM workers and their level of stress due to job responsibilities.
- **Alternative Hypothesis (H₁)** : There is a significant association between the job role of MESCOM workers and their level of stress due to job responsibilities.

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Job role of the respondents * Stress level of the Respondents	80	100.0%	0	0.0%	80	100.0%

Job role of the respondents * Stress level of the Respondents Crosstabulation

			Stress level of the Respondents					Total	
			Alwa ys	Ofte n	Someti mes	Rare ly	Neve r		
Job role of the respondents	Field staff	Count	1	2	5	1	0	9	
		Expected Count	.7	.7	6.3	1.1	.2	9.0	
	Office staff	Count	1	1	12	2	1	17	
		Expected Count	1.3	1.3	11.9	2.1	.4	17.0	
	Line man	Count	2	1	32	6	0	41	
		Expected Count	3.1	3.1	28.7	5.1	1.0	41.0	
	Super visor	Count	2	1	7	1	1	12	
		Expected Count	.9	.9	8.4	1.5	.3	12.0	
	Others	Count	0	1	0	0	0	1	
		Expected Count	.1	.1	.7	.1	.0	1.0	
	Total		Count	6	6	56	10	2	80
			Expected Count	6.0	6.0	56.0	10.0	2.0	80.0

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	23.221 ^a	16	.108
Likelihood Ratio	15.802	16	.467
N of Valid Cases	80		
a. 20 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03.			

Results (Chi-Square Test)

The Chi-Square test was conducted to examine the relationship between the job role of MESCOM workers and their level of stress due to job responsibilities. The results showed a Pearson Chi-Square value of 23.221 with 16 degrees of freedom and a significance level (p-value) of 0.108. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) could not be rejected.

Interpretation

This indicates that there is no statistically significant association between the job role of MESCOM workers and their stress levels arising from job responsibilities. In other words, the stress level of workers does not appear to depend on their job role in the present study sample. However, as 80% of the cells had expected counts less than 5, the reliability of this test result may be limited.

4.27. Chi-Square Test between Mental exhaustion after work And Satisfaction with work-life balance

- **Null Hypothesis (H₀)** : There is no significant association between the frequency of mental exhaustion after work and the level of satisfaction with work-life balance among MESCOM workers.
- **Alternative Hypothesis (H₁)** : There is a significant association between the frequency of mental exhaustion after work and the level of satisfaction with work-life balance among MESCOM workers.

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Work life balance satisfaction of the Respondents * Mental Exhaustion of the Respondents	80	100.0%	0	0.0%	80	100.0%

Work life balance satisfaction of the Respondents * Mental Exhaustion of the Respondents Crosstabulation

			Mental Exhaustion of the Respondents					Total	
			Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never		
Work life balance satisfaction of the Respondents	very satisfied	Count	1	0	3	0	1	5	
		Expected Count	.3	.5	3.4	.6	.2	5.0	
	Satisfied	Count	0	4	19	6	0	29	
		Expected Count	1.5	2.9	19.9	3.6	1.1	29.0	
	Neutral	Count	1	4	29	3	2	39	
		Expected Count	2.0	3.9	26.8	4.9	1.5	39.0	
	Dissatisfied	Count	1	0	4	1	0	6	
		Expected Count	.3	.6	4.1	.8	.2	6.0	
	Very Dissatisfied	Count	1	0	0	0	0	1	
		Expected Count	.1	.1	.7	.1	.0	1.0	
	Total		Count	4	8	55	10	3	80
			Expected Count	4.0	8.0	55.0	10.0	3.0	80.0

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	34.614 ^a	16	.004
Likelihood Ratio	22.576	16	.126
N of Valid Cases	80		
a. 23 cells (92.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.			

Results (Chi-Square Test)

The Chi-Square test was conducted to examine the relationship between mental exhaustion after work and work-life balance satisfaction of MESCOM workers. The analysis revealed a Pearson Chi-Square value of 34.614 with 16 degrees of freedom and a significance level (p-value) of 0.004. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Interpretation

This shows that there is a statistically significant association between the two variables. In other words, the level of work-life balance satisfaction among employees is strongly related to how often they experience mental exhaustion after work. Employees with higher levels of exhaustion are more likely to feel dissatisfied with their work-life balance, while those with lower exhaustion levels report greater satisfaction. However, as 92% of the cells had expected counts less than 5, the reliability of the result may be limited.

CHAPTER -5
FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

Findings of the Study

- 1. Age and Experience** – Most of the 80 MESCOM workers surveyed are in the 26–45 age group, showing that the organization has a largely mid-career workforce. This also means workers are experienced but exposed to stress for many years.
- 2. Gender Distribution** – The majority of respondents are male, reflecting the physically demanding and risk-oriented nature of the electricity sector, though a few female employees are also present.
- 3. Marital and Family Status** – A large share of respondents are married, which suggests that workplace stress extends into family life, affecting relationships and work–life balance.
- 4. Educational Qualification** – Most employees hold technical qualifications (diploma/ITI/engineering), highlighting that stress is being faced by skilled professionals who carry heavy responsibility for maintaining power supply.
- 5. Job Role and Tenure** – Many workers reported being in the same role for several years, leading to monotony, lack of growth opportunities, and increased organizational stress.
- 6. Workload and Hours** – Long working hours, irregular shifts, and emergency duties were identified as major causes of stress. Workers are often called out at night, during storms, or on holidays, which leads to fatigue.
- 7. Public Pressure** – Handling consumer complaints during outages and facing public anger was seen as a major emotional burden on employees.
- 8. Health and Well-being** – Workers reported stress-related health issues such as body pain, fatigue, headaches, lack of sleep, and low energy levels.
- 9. Family Impact** – Stress negatively affected family time. Employees said irregular hours and fatigue led to missing family functions, strained relationships, and less time with children.
- 10. Organizational Issues** – Delayed promotions, lack of recognition, and insufficient staff support were seen as sources of dissatisfaction and stress.
- 11. Safety Concerns** – Field workers highlighted the risk of accidents while climbing poles, handling wires, and working in bad weather. This constant safety risk contributes to stress.

12. Overall Picture – Stress in MESCOM is not caused by one factor but a **combination** of work conditions (long hours, emergencies, physical risks), organizational policies (recognition, career growth), and personal pressures (family responsibilities, health).

Suggestions of the Study

- 1. Reduce Workload** – Recruit more staff and distribute work evenly to prevent long and irregular working hours.
- 2. Stress Management Programs** – Organize counseling, yoga, meditation, or awareness workshops to help employees cope with stress.
- 3. Timely Recognition** – Appreciate employee efforts through rewards, promotions, and acknowledgment to boost morale.
- 4. Flexible Scheduling** – Introduce better shift management so employees can balance work and family life.
- 5. Health and Safety Support** – Provide regular health check-ups, safety gear, and rest breaks to reduce physical strain.
- 6. Employee Support Systems** – Create grievance redressal cells and support groups where employees can share issues without fear.
- 7. Training Programs** – Conduct training in stress management, safety, and technology use to reduce job-related anxiety.
- 8. Strengthen Communication** – Improve coordination between management and staff to reduce misunderstandings and build trust.
- 9. Family-Friendly Policies** – Organize welfare programs and family support initiatives to reduce the personal impact of stress.
- 10. Long-Term Measures** – Focus on manpower planning, infrastructure improvement, and continuous support systems to reduce chronic stress.

CHAPTER- 6
CONCLUSION

CONCLUSION

Work-related stress is a reality that no organization can ignore, especially in demanding sectors such as electricity supply. It is not simply an individual issue but a collective challenge that directly influences productivity, safety, efficiency, and even customer satisfaction. The experiences shared by MESCOM employees make it clear that while stress cannot be eliminated entirely, its intensity and impact can be significantly reduced through proper organizational strategies and support.

The workforce studied represents a group of employees who are deeply committed to their duties but often stretched beyond healthy limits. Most are in the 26–45 age range, balancing professional and personal responsibilities simultaneously. Irregular work shifts, shortage of manpower, long working hours, and the constant public expectation of uninterrupted electricity supply add layers of pressure. Safety hazards further compound this stress, creating a working environment that is both physically and mentally demanding. The spillover effect of these challenges is evident in employees' personal lives, where health concerns and family strain become unavoidable consequences.

The findings also show that stress among employees arises not from a single source but from the interaction of multiple factors—operational challenges, organizational gaps, and personal responsibilities. Lack of recognition for hard work, limited avenues for career growth, and insufficient welfare measures intensify the pressure. Yet, despite these difficulties, employees demonstrate remarkable resilience and a sense of responsibility, consistently ensuring uninterrupted electricity supply even in adverse circumstances. This sense of duty underscores the need for organizational reciprocation in the form of structured stress management programs and employee-friendly policies.

From a managerial perspective, stress must be addressed as a strategic priority. Employee well-being is not just about personal health; it directly translates into organizational performance, safety outcomes, and customer trust. Managers and leaders must therefore move away from viewing stress management as a secondary concern. Instead, they should invest in manpower planning, proper shift rotations, transparent career progression, continuous training, recognition and reward systems, and regular wellness initiatives. Even simple steps like counseling services and stress-relief workshops can make a meaningful difference.

The broader implication of this study is that stress can act both as a threat and an opportunity. If neglected, it drains morale, reduces efficiency, and weakens the organization's culture. However, when acknowledged and addressed, it provides an opportunity to redesign systems and build a healthier, more resilient, and future-ready workforce. An organization that values its employees as human assets—rather than just resources—can foster loyalty, motivation, and innovation.

Ultimately, the strength of an organization lies in the well-being of its people. A motivated and stress-resilient workforce not only ensures uninterrupted service but also strengthens the trust of the community it serves. By placing employee welfare at the heart of its strategy, MESCOM has the potential to enhance both organizational sustainability and social impact. In the long run, prioritizing employee well-being is not just an act of responsibility but an investment in the future of the organization and the society it supports.

CHAPTER -7
BIBLIOGRAPHY

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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CHAPTER- 8

ANNEXURE

Questionnaire

1. Age

- Below 25
- 26–35
- 36–45
- 46 and above

2. 2.Gender

- Male
- Female
- Other:

3. Marital Status

- Married
- Unmarried
- Other

4. Educational Qualification

- SSLC
- PUC
- Diploma
- Graduate
- Postgraduate
- Other:

5. Job Role in MESCOM

- Field Staff
- Office Staff
- Line Man
- Supervisor
- Other:

6. Years of Service in MESCOM

- Less than 1 year
- 1–3 years
- 4–6 years
- Above 6 years

7. Do you feel stressed due to your job responsibilities?

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

8. What are your main sources of stress at work? (Select all that apply)

- Long working hours
- Dealing with customers/public pressure
- Lack of staff
- Deadlines and targets
- Physical workload
- Lack of recognition
- Poor communication from management

9. How would you rate your workload?

- Very high
- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Very low

10. Do you receive clear instructions and communication from your supervisors?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes

11. How frequently do you experience physical symptoms of stress (e.g., fatigue, headaches, body pain)?

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Rarely
- Never

12. How often do you feel mentally exhausted after work?*

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

13. Does your job affect your personal or family life?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes

14. Do you feel pressure to meet unrealistic expectations or targets?

- Yes
- No
- Occasionally

15. Are you satisfied with your current work-life balance?

- Very Satisfied
- Satisfied
- Neutral
- Dissatisfied
- Very Dissatisfied

16. Do you think stress affects your job performance?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

17. How do you usually manage or reduce your stress? (Select all that apply)

- Talking to colleagues or family
- Taking breaks
- Yoga or meditation
- Exercise or sports
- Ignore it / Don't cope actively
- Other:

18. Does MESCOM provide any support (like counseling, seminars, welfare programs) to help manage stress?

- Yes
- No
- Not aware

19. Are you comfortable talking to your manager/supervisor about work stress?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

20. Have you received any stress management training or workshops from MESCOM?

- Yes
- No
- Not aware

21. Do you think MESCOM's management is concerned about worker well-being?

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

22. What do you think MESCOM can do to reduce employee stress?

23. Would you recommend stress-related training or wellness sessions in MESCOM?*

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

24. Any additional comments or suggestions?